

Beyond Borders: The Role of Language in Global Research-to-Policy Dynamics

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Background

Data and Methods

overton

Citation chaining:

- Policy citing research
- Policy citing policy

Image: one of the examples from <https://www.overton.io/how-to-use-overton-to-track-influence-and-impact/>

Read to learn more about Overton:

Martin Szomszor, Euan Adie; Overton: A bibliometric database of policy document citations.

Quantitative Science Studies 2022; 3 (3): 624–650. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00204

Study Workflow

Full report, data, and Python script are available:
Shenmeng Xu (2024). Beyond Borders: The Role of Language in
Global Research-to-Policy Dynamics <https://osf.io/8x3gf/>

Three Case Studies

- Topic: school bullying

Scholarly articles on this topic -> citing policy documents -> citing policy documents

- Topic: gender equity

Scholarly articles on this topic -> citing policy documents -> citing policy documents

- Topic: the Fukushima nuclear water discharge

Policy documents on this topic -> citing policy documents

Case Study I: Overview

Case Study I: Time from Science to Policy

Bubble Chart of Citation Lag and Count by Citing Policy Document Language (unit: day)

Case Study I: Language Flows in Citations

Policy-to-Policy Citation Pathways

A Policy-to-Policy Citation Pathway Example

	International Native	International English	Local Native	Local English
International English	Yes	N/A	Not Observed	N/A
International Native	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Local English	Not Observed	N/A	Not Observed	N/A
Local Native	Not Observed	Not Observed	Not Observed	Yes

Policy to Policy Citation Pathway Matrix based on Study Sample

Discussions

- **Case studies I and II uncovered some common patterns:**
 - similar reach in terms of both languages and countries
 - the critical role of policy-to-policy citations in addition to research-to-policy translation
 - common language patterns: Spanish was the most “influential” language following English; French and Finnish emerged as “quick” languages; “longevity” of languages were similar; etc.
- **Case studies I and II also highlighted critical differences:** e.g., countries in Case Study I overall had higher percentages of policy documents in native languages than those in Case Study II, due to the distinct local relevancy of the topics of school bullying and gender equity.

Discussions

- Policy documents authored by IGOs in multiple language versions played an essential role in translating scientific implications and policy among languages.
- The absence of citation pathways from **Local** to **International** might be explained by:
 - lack of relevance
 - language barrier – more policy documents in native languages
 - lack of coverage of local policy documents in native languages from these East Asian countries (at least Mainland China, as found by Yin et al., 2021) in Overton database
 - some countries do not commonly practice officially citing scientific articles in policy documents (Ren & Yang, 2022)
 - local government agencies were less likely to cite science than IGOs and think tanks due to the nature of their policy documents – citations to scholarly articles occur more as markers of evidence synthesis activities targeted towards policymakers rather than as indicators of legislative change and decision making (Yin et al., 2021; Pinheiro et al., 2021)

Acknowledgement

This project was supported by funding from the Overton's Policy Data Impact Grant (2023-2024).

The 2024 CFP is open now: <https://www.overton.io/updates/overtons-policy-impact-grant-returns-for-2024-apply-now/>

Additional References

Pinheiro, H., Vignola-Gagné, E., & Campbell, D. (2021). A large-scale validation of the relationship between cross-disciplinary research and its uptake in policy-related documents, using the novel Overton altmetrics database. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1–27. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00137

Ren, C., & Yang, M. (2023). Study on the Characteristics of CROSS-DOMAIN Knowledge Diffusion from Science to Policy: Evidence from Overton Data. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 60(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pr2.795>

Yin, Y., Gao, J., Jones, B. F., & Wang, D. (2021). Coevolution of policy and science during the pandemic. *Science*, 371(6525), Article 6525. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe3084>

Thank you!

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